

POLICY DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING LUMPUE TYPE A TERMINAL SERVICE FACILITIES BASED ON SERVICE STANDARDS AND ASPIRATIONS OF SERVICE USERS IN THE CITY OF PARE-PARE

Hidayatullah M¹, Arifuddin Akil² and Andi Bachtiar Arief³

¹ Student of Urban Management, Graduate School, Hasanuddin University, Makassar, Indonesia.

² Professor Department of Urban Planning, Hasanuddin University, Makassar, Indonesia.

³ Doctor of Urban Management, Graduate School, Hasanuddin University, Makassar, Indonesia.

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.11485344](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11485344)

Abstract

The terminal is a place that is really needed by the public for land transportation. Terminal facilities are grouped into main facilities and supporting/general facilities. This research aims to: (1) describe the condition of the Parepare Type A Main Terminal service facilities; (2) obtain the level of service user satisfaction with the Parepare Type A Main Terminal service facilities; (3) developing the aspirations of service users regarding service standards for the Parepare Type A Main Terminal. The data analysis used is quadrant analysis or Importance Performance Analysis (IPA). The results of the research show that the condition of the main and supporting service facilities at the Lumpue Main Terminal Type A, Parepare City is in very good condition, quite adequate and comfortable for service users, but there are several things that need to be improved. Terminal Type A Main Lumpue, Parepare City shows that the services at the terminal are in accordance with the criteria based on PM No. 40 of 2015 with a greater percentage that can be used and only a few are inadequate and none.

Keywords: Terminal Facilities, Terminal Type A.

INTRODUCTION

Transportation has an important and strategic role in development. Therefore, planning and development must be organized into one complete system [1]. To achieve smooth and good integration between modes of transportation, a terminal will be created that supports accessibility and a good circulation system inside (between environments) and outside (through the city so that traffic can be managed effectively and efficiently) [1].

The terminal is the entry and exit point for passengers and goods, which is an important part of the transportation system. Terminal processing must be carried out thoroughly, because this terminal is infrastructure that requires quite high costs and is a place where congestion occurs [2].

The presence of a terminal is very important for the smooth and controlled implementation of intra-transportation and inter-modal integration. Basically, a terminal is a node in a road transportation network system which consists of two types of terminals, namely. (1) Passenger terminal and (2) cargo terminal. Both are road transportation for picking up and dropping off passengers/goods as well as regulating the arrival and departure of public vehicles so that the terminal must be managed and maintained so that it can meet the needs of the community and road traffic well and include the facilities and infrastructure owned by the terminal [3].

Passenger terminal service standards are guidelines for road transport terminal operators in providing services. Decree of the Minister of Transportation Number 24 of 2021 concerning the operation of road transport passenger terminals states that

every passenger terminal operator is obliged to provide terminal facilities that meet safety and security requirements. The passenger terminal facilities in question consist of main facilities, supporting facilities and general facilities [4].

Terminal Classification according to Minister of Transportation Decree No. 31 of 1996 concerning road transport terminals, namely: Type A terminal is the main terminal that serves inter-provincial city transport, and state border traffic, intra-provincial city transport, intra-city transport, and rural transport. Type B terminal is a terminal that serves inter-city and provincial, intra-city and rural transportation. Type C terminal is a terminal that only serves intra-city transportation and rural transportation.

Lumpue Type A Terminal is located in Lumpue Village, West Bacukiki District, Parepare City. Lumpue Terminal is the main terminal that connects traffic nodes for various improvements in facilities and infrastructure. Its existence is very important to encourage travel efficiency (using public transportation) for the people of Parepare and increase regional primary income. The management of the Lumpue terminal is completely handed over to the Ministry of Transportation.

Current regional government policies prioritize public services. The general view of the government revolves around public satisfaction, it is important to design and use public attitudes as an index of the quality of a country's public services. Based on this information, policy patterns and opinions, as the population increases from year to year, the number of passengers also increases, which can lead to inequality. Between supplies and needs which can trigger a decline in the quality of terminal services [5]. So, this has an impact on passenger/customer service. Therefore, it is necessary to study the service quality of the Lumpue Type a Terminal.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Research Location

The location of this research was carried out at the Lumpue Main Type a Terminal, which is located in the Lumpue Village area, West Bacukiki District, Parepare City. Lumpue Village itself is a flexible area which has a beach and borders directly with Barru Regency.

Population and Sample

The research population is the research that will be studied covering the entire object. The population referred to in this research are terminal employees, the community around the terminal, and buses entering the terminal (passengers and drivers). The population in this study was 3600 respondents (results of data collection in January and February 2023).

A sample is a small portion used to represent the entire population in a study. Based on the results of Slovin's calculations, a sample size of 100 people was obtained.

Data Collection

Data collection is a very important stage in research. Therefore, author use several research techniques to support the success and validity of this research, the techniques used:

Primary Data

Observation is the process of using the senses, such as sight, smell, and hearing, to collect data necessary to answer a research question. Observation results include various activities, events, objects, situations and emotional aspects of individuals. Documentation in this research takes the form of photographs related to the variables that will be discussed in this research. The questionnaire method was applied to collect primary data from visitors to the Type A passenger terminal in Lumpue. The questions have been designed to elicit relevant information about the aspects and attributes of the service that are to be investigated. The preparation of the questionnaire is based on a service quality approach, the questionnaire consists of several statements which are divided into several parts.

The statement regarding the identification of service perceptions, measuring customer perceptions of service quality contains statements representing the five variables in service quality, the assessment is carried out by respondents using a 1 - 4 Likert scale for each statement.

Secondary Data

Secondary data collection is carried out at related agencies. The supporting data needed to complete this thesis is data obtained from the Ministry of Transportation or related agencies, including: data on the number of vehicles and passengers for each route, data on the number of passenger arrivals and departures, as well as type A terminal service standard data.

Data Analysis

Data analysis used in this research is based on research questions, namely: To answer the first research question in this study, qualitative descriptive analysis was used. Qualitative descriptive analysis to determine the existing conditions and availability of terminal service facility needs based on the 2021 PM Ministry of Transportation standards. The data analysis technique used to answer the second formulation of the problem is Importance Performance Analysis. Importance-Performance Analysis consists of two components, namely: Quadrant analysis and Gap analysis. In this research, researchers used Quadrant Analysis to evaluate consumer responses to the services provided by Lumpue Type A Terminal managers. Through assessing the level of satisfaction and performance, the level of suitability between the level of importance and the level of implementation will be calculated. The horizontal axis (X) will reflect the implementation level score, while the vertical axis (Y) will depict the importance/expectation level score. The next step is to calculate the average level of importance and performance for all indicators. The average score of the performance assessment level from the respondents will then be placed on a Cartesian diagram with the horizontal axis (X axis) being the average score of the performance assessment level and the vertical axis (Y axis) being the average score of the indicator's importance/expectation assessment level. This Cartesian diagram will be divided into four quadrants with the intersection of the axes being the total average value of the performance assessment score X and the total importance/expectation assessment score Y.

Picture 1: Diagram of Importance and Performance Analysis

The Importance and Performance Analysis diagram consists of four quadrants with a description of each quadrant as follows [6].

- 1) Quadrant I (Main Priority): This is an area where service indicators have a large impact on service user satisfaction, but their performance is less than satisfactory and requires priority improvement.
- 2) Quadrant II (Maintain Performance): Here, existing services show importance and have high performance. These services need to be maintained at a high level of performance for the next period.
- 3) Quadrant III (Low Priority): Service indicators in this quadrant are considered less important by service users, and their performance is not special. Improvements in service indicators here may need to be revised, because their impact on service user satisfaction is relatively small.
- 4) Quadrant IV (Excessive): This is the area where service indicators are not very important for service user satisfaction, and performance exceeds expectations. Therefore, there is no need for further (excessive) improvements.

To answer the third research question, qualitative and quantitative analysis was used, which was carried out descriptively by identifying the availability of Lumpue Main Type a Terminal service facilities. This analysis aims to describe the availability of the data that has been collected, so as to obtain a general and comprehensive picture of the actual situation by comparing the data that has been collected according to the terminal service standards from the Minister of Transportation in 2021. So that it can determine policy directions for improving service facilities and aspirations of service users at the Type a Lumpue terminal, Parepare city.

RESULTS

Condition of Service Facilities

As is common for public service places, land transportation terminals must also have adequate facilities so that they can carry out their function in serving the needs of their

users. Land transport terminal facility standards have been regulated in the Minister of Transportation Republic of Indonesia No. 132 of 2015. The condition of service facilities at the Lumpue Type a Main Terminal is categorized into two types, namely main facilities and general/supporting facilities, which can be seen below:

Table 1: Condition of Service Facilities at the Lumpue Main Type A Terminal.

Service Facilities	Condition			Information
	There is	There isn't any	Amount	
Main Facilities				
Departure route public transport	√	-	2	Good
Public transportation arrival route	√	-	2	Good
Waiting place passenger or delivery person	√	-	2	Good
Place for passengers to get on and off	√	-	1	
Public transportation parking area	√	-	1	Good & quite spacious
Ticket sales counter	√	-	4	Good
Signs and information boards that at least contain instructions for courses, rates and schedules journey (road equipment)	√	-		Temporary repair
Information media	√	-		
Terminal operator's office	√	-		
Supporting/General Facilities				
Bathroom / WC	√	-	6	Fairly Good (4 Repaired and 2 unused)
Worship facilities	√	-	1	Good
Facilities for people with disabilities and pregnant women or breastfeeding	√	-	1	Good
Health facilities	√	-	1	Good (Not yet Used)
Police station	√	-	1	Good
Fire extinguishers	√	-	4	Good
Telecommunication facilities	-	√		There isn't any
Your resting place vehicle	-	√		There isn't any
Facilities for reducing pollution to noise	-	√		There isn't any
Restaurant	-	√		There isn't any
Air and exhaust gas quality monitoring facilities	-	√		There isn't any
Cleaning facilities	√	-	2	Not enough adequate
Public vehicle light repair facilities	-	√		There isn't any
Trading facilities & shops	√	-	4	Not enough adequate
Lodging facilities	-	√		There isn't any

The condition of public facilities at the Lumpue Type A Main Terminal was found to be 2 departure lanes for public vehicles in good condition, 2 arrival lanes in good condition, 2 waiting areas for passengers or delivery people in good condition, there is one place for passengers to get on and off, and there is a vehicle parking area. The general area is quite spacious and good, there are 4 ticket sales counters in good condition, there are signs and information boards which at least contain directions,

fares and travel schedules (road equipment), information media is available, and the organizer's office is available at the terminal.

Based on the results of the condition of supporting facilities, it was found that 6 bathrooms/WCs of which 2 were not used and 4 were quite good, there was a worship facility in good condition, there was a facility for people with disabilities and pregnant or breastfeeding mothers, there was a health facility that had not been used, there was a post the police are in good condition, there are 4 fire extinguishers in good condition, there are no restaurant/canteen facilities, there are cleaning facilities, and there are inadequate trading/shopping facilities. Meanwhile, there were no telecommunications facilities, vehicle crew rest areas, noise pollution production facilities, air and exhaust gas quality monitoring facilities, light repair facilities for public vehicles, and lodging facilities.

Level of Appropriateness of Respondents' Service Facilities to the Aspirations of Service Users at Lumpue Main Terminal Type A

Table 2: Conformity level test results by comparing the level of facilities and service users

No.	Statements	$\sum X$	$\sum Y$	Level of conformity	%
1	P1	327	344	0.95	95
2	P2	324	341	0.95	95
3	P3	321	338	0.95	95
4	P4	329	339	0.97	97
5	P5	323	345	0.94	94
6	P6	318	337	0.94	94
7	P7	308	331	0.93	93
8	P8	307	329	0.93	93
9	P9	321	322	1.00	100
10	P10	313	311	1.01	101
11	P11	302	325	0.93	93
12	P12	308	342	0.90	90
13	P13	215	343	0.63	63
14	P14	311	332	0.94	94
15	P15	207	327	0.63	63
16	P16	308	322	0.96	96
17	P17	301	331	0.91	91
18	P18	310	322	0.96	96
19	P19	308	334	0.92	92
20	P20	331	363	0.91	91
21	P21	334	331	1.01	101
22	P22	323	326	0.99	99
23	P23	321	353	0.91	91
24	P24	322	319	1.01	101
25	P25	317	339	0.94	94
Average				0.92	92

The results of the level of conformity of the 25 statements were obtained from the results of the facility level questionnaire assessment ($\sum X$) divided by the results of the service user level questionnaire assessment ($\sum Y$) and the results were multiplied by 100%. The average result of calculating the respondent's level of suitability was 92%. The average result was obtained from the total number of statements and then the

results were divided by the 19 statements. It can be said that the level of facilities, both public and supporting facilities, are able to meet the expectations of service users, which means that service users are satisfied with the 25 facility statements at the Lumpue Main Terminal Type A, Parepare City, but the facilities need to be improved.

Level of Service Facilities for the Aspirations of Lumpue Main Terminal Service Users Type A in Parepare City

After analyzing the level of suitability of facilities and service users, the next step is to find out the average level of service facilities and the average level of service users provided by respondents.

Table 3: The average level of service facilities and the average level of service users provided by respondents

No.	Statements	$\sum X$	$\sum Y$	Average X	Average Y
1	P1	327	344	3.27	3.44
2	P2	324	341	3.24	3.41
3	P3	321	338	3.21	3.38
4	P4	329	339	3.29	3.39
5	P5	323	345	3.23	3.45
6	P6	318	337	3.18	3.37
7	P7	308	331	3.08	3.31
8	P8	307	329	3.07	3.29
9	P9	321	322	3.21	3.22
10	P10	313	311	3.13	3.11
11	P11	302	325	3.02	3.25
12	P12	308	342	3.08	3.42
13	P13	215	343	2.15	3.43
14	P14	311	332	3.11	3.32
15	P15	207	327	2.07	3.27
16	P16	308	322	3.08	3.22
17	P17	301	331	3.01	3.31
18	P18	310	322	3.10	3.22
19	P19	308	334	3.08	3.34
20	P20	331	363	3.31	3.63
21	P21	334	331	3.34	3.31
22	P22	323	326	3.23	3.26
23	P23	321	353	3.21	3.53
24	P24	322	319	3.22	3.19
25	P25	317	339	3.17	3.39
Average				3.04	3.32

The X and Y values are the average values of 100 respondents, namely Terminal Service Users, from the results of the assessment of the service facility level statement (X) and service user level statement (Y). The X value is obtained from the results of assessing the level of service facilities (X) divided by 100 respondents, likewise the Y value is obtained from the results of assessing the level of service users (Y) divided by 100 respondents. Based on the calculations in table 19, the average value of X and Y is obtained, which is equal to 3,04 and 3,32. The average value is obtained from the sum of the average values of X and Y divided by 25 statements. This value is used as a barrier between the average values of X and Y which intersect to form four parts.

Next, the results from the table are described in a Cartesian diagram, and the results can be seen in the image below:

Picture 2: Cartesian Diagram of Importance and Performance Analysis

Based on the results of the Importance Performance Analysis analysis on the Cartesian diagram, it shows that there are 4 quadrants, namely:

- a) Quadrant 1 (Main priority) is a comfortable passenger/delivery waiting room (13), posts, facilities and health workers (12), and comfortable toilets, WC (19).
- b) Quadrant 2 (Maintain performance) is the importance of providing a written vehicle arrival schedule (1), the importance of providing a written vehicle departure schedule (2), adequate ticket/ticket sales counters (3), terminal organizer office buildings whose locations can be reached easily (4), terminal operational officers (5), availability of information boards that at least contain directions, fares and travel schedules that are easy to understand (6), level of ease of reaching the terminal location (20), costs incurred by the public from the city center or the housing center to the terminal or vice versa is affordable for the public (23), and the level of ease in obtaining information in the terminal (25).
- c) Quadrant 3 (Low priority) is officers in the information and complaints room who are quite responsive (7), security officers maintain order for terminal users (8), complete service information is available (11), comfortable atmosphere in the canteen (15), availability many choices of food/drink menus in the canteen (16), and there are terminal cleaning staff (17).
- d) Quadrant 4 (Excessive) is the room lighting in the terminal (9), the availability of adequate treatment rooms (10), the prayer/prayer facilities provided are quite comfortable (14), reliable storage for goods (18), easy city transportation network support obtained from housing and the city center to the terminal or vice versa (21), the availability of feeder connections to the terminal or vice versa (22), and the level of ease of getting tickets and changing modes (24).

At the beginning of the existence of the Lumpue Main Type A Terminal, it is hoped that city transportation, coming in and out of the city, which is destined/originating from the city of Parepare will no longer need to enter the city center, but only until the terminal, then the passengers will be transported by city transportation into the city. Optimization of terminal functions is encouraged so that there is order in operational and data collection administration, the public's interest in terminal services is increasingly urgent and the terminal is obliged to carry out adequate government functions and services supported by a work system that supports public expectations. The following are service facilities that are inadequate and not at the Lumpue Main Type A Terminal.

Table 4: Service Facilities at the Lumpue Main Type A Terminal

Service Facilities	There is	There isn't any	Information
Medical facility	√	-	Inadequate
Cleaning Facilities	√	-	Inadequate
Trading Facilities/ Shops	√	-	Inadequate
Telecommunication Facilities	-	√	
Crew Rest Facilities Vehicle	-	√	
Pollution Reduction Facilities	-	√	
Public Vehicle Repair Facility	-	√	
Eating House/Restaurant	-	√	
Lodging Facilities	-	√	

Based on the table above regarding service facilities, the results of the explanation regarding the condition and adequacy of service facilities are inadequate and several facilities have not been found at the Lumpue Main Type A terminal. Inadequate service facilities include health facilities, cleaning facilities, and trade/shopping facilities, while service facilities that are not yet available include telecommunications facilities, vehicle crew rest areas, pollution reduction, repair of public transportation, restaurants, and lodging. This is because the condition of the Lumpue Parepare Main Type A Terminal is still being repaired so that some service facilities are inadequate or not even available.

DISCUSSION

The condition of the main and supporting service facilities at the Lumpue Type A Main Terminal in Parepare City is in very good condition, quite adequate and comfortable for service users, however there are several things that need to be improved, such as telecommunications facilities, vehicle crew rest areas, noise pollution reduction facilities, a place to monitor air and exhaust gas quality, repair light vehicles, as well as lodging facilities for service users. This is in line with the Minister of Transportation Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia No. 132 of 2015 concerning standards for land transportation terminal facilities. In this Ministerial Regulation, the facilities required to be present in a terminal are categorized into three types, namely main facilities, supporting facilities and general facilities [7].

The following are the results of the suitability level test by comparing the level of facilities and service users, which can be seen in table 2. It can be seen that the level of facilities for service users at Lumpue Main Terminal Type A, the lowest at 63%, is the information and complaints room for service facilities, while for the level of satisfaction of service users, namely a comfortable atmosphere in the canteen. This shows that this statement still does not satisfy respondents because the information

room and place for complaints are still in the process of being repaired, while the level of satisfaction of service users, namely the comfortable atmosphere of the canteen, does not satisfy respondents because the terminal area still lacks canteens/restaurants for terminal service users [8].

The terminal facility statements that received the highest suitability level of 101% and exceeded respondents' expectations were 3 statements, namely from the facility level, namely parking equipment for delivery vehicles or taxis, safe places for passengers to get on and off, and the availability of disabled facilities [9]. This shows that the terminal staff really pay attention to the parking equipment for delivery vehicles or taxis so that users park their vehicles in an orderly manner, so that terminal users feel very satisfied with the facilities at the terminal. Meanwhile, the satisfaction of service users is the availability of adequate treatment rooms, easy access to city transportation network support from housing and the city center to the terminal or vice versa, and the level of ease of getting tickets and changing modes [10].

The average result of calculating the respondent's level of suitability was 92%. The average result was obtained from the total number of statements and then the results were divided by the 19 statements. It can be said that the level of facilities, both public and supporting facilities, are able to meet the expectations of service users, which means that service users are satisfied with the 25 facility statements at the Lumpue Main Terminal Type A, Parepare City, but the facilities need to be improved. According to Prabantari 2020, service user satisfaction has a significant relationship with service quality, in this case service facilities, where if service facilities are complete and adequate, the level of service user satisfaction will increase [11].

Based on the research that has been carried out, the results show what statements are considered important by service users when they are at the Lumpue Type A Main Terminal. Based on the results of the analysis of what is considered important using the Importance Performance Analysis method, the following are several things that can be implied to the Transportation Service in accordance with the research results, namely as follows.

Quadrant 1 (Main priority) shows what is considered important by service users but the manager has not shown good performance. The statements that fall into this quadrant are: comfortable passenger/delivery waiting room, post, facilities and health workers, and comfortable toilets/WC.

Quadrant 2 (Maintain performance) shows statements that are considered important by service users and have been implemented well by the management. Statements included in quadrant 2 are the importance of providing a written vehicle arrival schedule, the importance of providing a written vehicle departure schedule, adequate ticket/ticket sales counters, terminal organizer office buildings whose location can be reached easily, terminal operational officers, the availability of information boards at least - lack of instructions for directions, fares and travel schedules that are easy to understand, the level of ease in reaching the terminal location, the costs incurred by the public from the city center or residential center to the terminal or vice versa are affordable for the public, and the level of ease in obtaining information in the terminal.

Quadrant 3 (Low priority) shows statements that are considered less important by respondents and management performance is also considered less good. The statements received by officers in the information and complaints room are quite responsive, security officers maintain order for terminal users, complete service

information is available, the atmosphere in the canteen is comfortable, there are many choices of food/drink menus in the canteen, and there are terminal cleaning officers.

Quadrant 4 (Excessive) shows statements that are less important according to respondents, but the management has given their best so that service users feel that these statements are excessive. Statements that fall into quadrant 4 are room lighting in the terminal, adequate treatment rooms are available, the prayer/prayer facilities provided are quite comfortable, reliable storage for goods, support from the city transportation network is easy to get from housing and the city center to the terminal or on the other hand, the availability of feeder connections to the terminal or vice versa, and the level of ease of getting tickets and changing modes.

Service facilities as a result of the description of table 1 regarding the condition and adequacy of service facilities are inadequate and several facilities have not been found at the Type A Main Lumpue terminal are in table 4. Inadequate service facilities include health facilities, cleaning facilities and trade facilities /shops, while service facilities that are not yet available include telecommunications facilities, vehicle crew rest areas, pollution reduction, public transportation repairs, restaurants and accommodation. This is because the condition of the Lumpue Parepare Main Type A Terminal is still in the repair stage so that several service facilities (main and supporting) are inadequate or not even available.

Based on the regulation of the Minister of Transportation of the Republic of Indonesia Number PM 24 of 2021 concerning service facility standards that must be met from type B terminal up to type A terminal, it is the availability of adequate service facilities and meeting minimum service standards. However, based on the results of this research, it shows that there are several facilities that are inadequate and do not exist because the condition of the Lumpue Main Type a Terminal is still under construction/renovation.

Based on the results of data analysis, it can be concluded that the Lumpue Main Type a Terminal currently has quite complete facilities, but its operations have not been carried out optimally. From the results data on Terminal Service Conditions Based on Service Standards for Type A Terminal Organizers in Main Lumpue, Parepare City, it shows that the service at the Type A Terminal in Main Lumpue meets the criteria based on PM No. 40 of 2015 with a greater percentage that can be used and only a few are inadequate and none.

CONCLUSION

Based on the research that has been carried out, in accordance with the problem formulation that has been described previously, a conclusion is obtained in the form of an answer to the research problem formulation. The following are the conclusions of the research, namely: The condition of the main and supporting service facilities at the Lumpue Type A Main Terminal in Parepare City is in very good condition, quite adequate and comfortable for service users, however there are several things that need to be improved, such as telecommunications facilities, vehicle crew rest areas, noise pollution reduction facilities, a place to monitor air and exhaust gas quality, repair light vehicles, as well as lodging facilities for service users. Based on the results of the analysis of the level of service facilities for service users using the Importance-Performance Analysis method, it is in Quadrant 1 (Main Priority) which shows what is considered important by service users but the management has not shown good

performance. The statements included in this quadrant are a comfortable passenger/delivery waiting room, post, facilities and health workers, and comfortable toilets/WC. Quadrant 2 (Maintain performance) shows statements that are considered important by service users and have been implemented well by the management. Statements included in quadrant 2 are the importance of providing a written vehicle arrival schedule, the importance of providing a written vehicle departure schedule, adequate ticket/ticket sales counters, terminal organizer office buildings whose location can be reached easily, terminal operational officers, the availability of information boards at least - lack of instructions for directions, fares and travel schedules that are easy to understand, the level of ease in reaching the terminal location, the costs incurred by the public from the city center or residential center to the terminal or vice versa are affordable for the public, and the level of ease in obtaining information in the terminal. Quadrant 3 (Low priority) shows statements that are considered less important by respondents and management performance is also considered less good. The statements received by officers in the information and complaints room are quite responsive, security officers maintain order for terminal users, complete service information is available, the atmosphere in the canteen is comfortable, there are many choices of food/drink menus in the canteen, and there are terminal cleaning officers. Quadrant 4 (Excessive) shows statements that are less important according to respondents, but the management has given their best so that service users feel that these statements are excessive. Statements that fall into quadrant 4 are room lighting in the terminal, adequate treatment rooms are available, the prayer/prayer facilities provided are quite comfortable, reliable storage for goods, support from the city transportation network is easy to get from housing and the city center to the terminal or on the other hand, the availability of feeder connections to the terminal or vice versa, and the level of ease of getting tickets and changing modes.

Based on the results of data analysis, it can be concluded that the Lumpue Main Type a Terminal currently has quite complete facilities, but its operation has not been carried out properly maximum. From the results data on Terminal Service Conditions, Based on Service Standards for Terminal Type A Main Lumpue, Parepare City, it shows that the services at the Type A Main Lumpue Terminal, Parepare City are in accordance with the criteria based on PM No. 40 of 2015 with a greater percentage that can be used and only a few. Which is inadequate and does not exist.

References

- 1) Aminah, S. Public Transportation and Urban Community Accessibility. *Journal of Civil Engineering*, 9(1), 1142-1155, 2018.
- 2) Priatama, A. N. Design of Standard Operational Procedures Regarding Traffic and Road Transport Safety Inspections at the Harjamukti Terminal, Cirebon City. *Road Transportation Safety Polytechnic*. Tegal, 2019.
- 3) Sadewo, R., Actress, Nuryanti, and Ismawartati. Obligation to Stop at the Terminal for Motorized Vehicles on Intercity Bus Routes (Batulayang Study). *Tanjungpura Legal Review*. Tanjungpura University, 2023.
- 4) Regulation of the Minister of Transportation of the Republic of Indonesia Number PM 24 of 2021 concerning Road Transport Passenger Terminal Operator.
- 5) Zulyaden. Analysis of the level of satisfaction of service users with terminal services in the city of Semarang, 2016.
- 6) Supranto, J. Measuring the level of customer satisfaction In (Vol. third printing). PT. RIN CIPTA Jakarta, 2006.

- 7) Asnawi. Alternative Terminal Location as a Center for Economic Growth in Doloksanggul, Humbang Hasundutan Regency. Regional and environmental journal. Diponegoro University. Semarang. Vol. 2(2): 113 – 128, 2014.
- 8) Nisa, N. F.. Evaluation of Bus Terminal Circulation Routes on Passenger Comfort at Mangkang Terminal, Semarang. Sinektika: Architectural Journal. Diponegoro University. Semarang. Vol. 20(2), 2023.
- 9) Andriyanto, D. D. Development of Tambak Osowilangun Type A Bus Terminal in Surabaya University August 17, 1945, 2018.
- 10) Saputra, M. Taufiq, Yuda. Analysis of the Level of Service User Satisfaction with the Service Performance of the Makassar Metro Makassar City Terminal. Ten November Institute of Technology. Surabaya, 2010.
- 11) Prabantari, B. V. K. Analysis of the relationship between Service Quality and the level of Transjakarta Transportation Customer Satisfaction. Transaction Journal. Vol. 12(1), 25–39, 2020.